

STUDY OF INTERNATIONAL ECOLOGICAL RELATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN HISTORIOGRAPHY

¹Sanjarbek Davletov, ²Ismail Nurmetov, ³Umida Tajieva

¹Doctor of Science (DSc), professor, Urgench State State University, Urgench, Uzbekistan

²Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Senior Lecturer of History Department, Urgench State University, Urgench, Uzbekistan

³PhD student of the Department of History, Urgench State University, Urgench, Uzbekistan

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Abstract. *This article illustrates that the issues of studying the aspects of international cooperation of the Republic of Uzbekistan related to ecology and environmental protection are analyzed during the years of independence. In particular, studies on the improvement of the environmental situation in the Aral Sea area, climate change, water resources management, biodiversity conservation, and the development of regional cooperation on environmental protection in Central Asia have been reflected. At the same time, the historiography of the research on cooperation relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan with international organizations is widely covered. Foreign publications covering some aspects of the activities of international organizations such as International Fund to Save the Aral Sea, the Interstate Water Management Coordinating Commission, the Central Asian Regional Ecological Center, were also analyzed.*

Key words: *Uzbekistan, Central Asia, international cooperation, ecology, transboundary rivers, historiography.*

Introduction

During the years of independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan, as an equal subject of international relations, has been paying attention to the improvement of important directions and legal foundations of international environmental political relations. In particular, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, organizational, legal and socio-economic measures to ensure environmental safety are consistently implemented. Implementation of international legal agreements and conventions into national legislation has become one of the main issues. International cooperation on ecology and environmental protection in the Republic of Uzbekistan is determined by the foreign policy strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Analysis and methodology of literature

The role of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the system of international relations, environmental issues in the internal and external political activities of the country, issues related to the protection of the environment in the Central Asian region on the basis of international cooperation, including the improvement of the environmental situation in Uzbekistan are considered to be one of the new directions of modern historiography of the history of Uzbekistan. Considering the scope of the researches and the created literature, it is appropriate to study them conditionally in two groups.

Among the literature belonging to the first group, a number of works and dissertations created in the years of independence in Uzbekistan are important. Among these are A. Kasimov, A. Kholiyev, Sunn Don Gi, D. Misharev, M. Rakhimov, E. Nuriddinov, Kh. Gulomov, A. Kholiyev, A. Kyrgyzboev, A. Sultanov, R. Asadova, D. Rahimbaeva, N. Gofurov and other authors of the country works related to the history of the development of political activity can be included. In these

works, the formation of the foreign political activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is an equal member of international relations, and the development processes in the first decade of independence are covered.

The second group consists of works by foreign authors. Among them are A. Akimov, I. Zvyagelskaya, V. Belokrinitsky, A. Kurtov, A. Perepelkin, D. Trofimov, S. Panarin, E. Safronova, historians, political scientists and other scientists of the CIS countries who conducted research related to the Central Asian region. The works of O. Tikhonov, A. Kazantsev, A. Vlasov, D. Nishanov, S. Yun, E. Troitsky, A. Bogaturov, A. Taylakova are particular interest in studying the problem.

The application of the principle of objectivity in research allows to minimize and eliminate the impact of subjective views on the research and its results as much as possible in the interpretation and assessment of evidence. From this point of view, the principles of historicity, scientific and impartiality, which constitute the dialectical foundations of scientific knowledge, are the theoretical methodological bases of the research, and the methods of historical-comparison, systematization, problem-chronological and interdisciplinary approach were used.

Analysis and results

To date, in various fields of social sciences, including history, law, philosophy and political sciences, development of regional cooperation on environmental protection in Central Asia, strengthening of good neighborly relations with countries in the region, elimination of transboundary problems, improvement of the environmental situation in the Aral Bay region, climate change, a number of researches focused on global environmental problems, such as water resources management, biodiversity conservation issues, were carried out.

It is important that a group of literature covers various aspects of the ecological situation in Uzbekistan. For example, publications published in the areas of ecology, law, and political science provide information on Uzbekistan's environmental policy, fulfillment of obligations under international agreements, and Uzbekistan's foreign policy. There are a number of sources related to ecology and environment in the coverage of issues related to international ecological cooperation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In particular, D. Bobojonova's "Aholi salomatligi va ekologik muammolar (Population health and environmental problems)", Kh. Tursunov's "Ekologiya asoslari va tabiatni muhofaza qilish (Fundamentals of Ecology and Nature Protection)", B. Kalonov, B. Ziyamuhamedov's "Ekologiya va madaniyat (Ecology and culture)", J. Kholmominov's "Ekologiya va qonun (Ecology and law)", A. Tokhtaev's In the books "Ekologiya (Ecology)", "Ekologiya nima? (What is ecology?)" by A. Nigmatov, "Ekologiya iqtisodiyoti (Ecology Economics)" by T.M. Jumaev, "Mintaqa ekologiyasini tartibga solish muammolari (Problems of regulation of regional ecology)" by N. Ikramova, and "Inson ekologiyasi (Human ecology)" by A. Ergashev, the impact of environmental problems on public health, environment - the role of the human factor in environmental protection, the legal solution of environmental issues in the legislation, the issues of cooperation carried out by social institutions and non-governmental non-profit organizations in stabilizing the environmental situation are covered in detail. In recent years of research in this direction, the current ecological situation in the country and the environmental problems that have arisen in this process have been discussed.

Political science scientific literature, monographs, doctoral theses, and scientific research papers reflect on the current environmental situation in the country and the global environmental problems that have arisen in this process. J. Kholmominov, D. Umarov's book "Uzbekistan Ekologik harakati va saylov qonunchiligi (Uzbekistan Ecological Movement and Electoral Legislation)", Sh.

Babaev's "Inson va ekologik omillar (Human and ecological factors)", B. Aslonov, N. Karimova's "Ekologicheskaya politika i bezopasnost", E. Danilova's "Ekologicheskiy monitoring nekotoryx rayonov Uzbekistana i zaboлеваemost", Sh. Fayziev's "Ekologicheskaya politika gosudarstva. Konsepsiya pravovogo obespechenia", A. Sanginov's "Aholi o'rtasida ekologik madaniyatni targ'ib etish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida (Measures to promote environmental culture among the population)", comments on the international ecological relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan were expressed.

Legal aspects of tasks related to the protection of nature, environment, improvement of sustainable ecological situation in the country are covered in legal studies. Among the representatives of this field are the study guide "Ekologiyaga doir qonunlar ijrosini tekshirish va qonunlar buzilishiga barham berish (Checking the implementation of ecology laws and the abolition of laws)" by T. Mirzaev, the book "Ekologiya nazoratini amalga oshiruvchi davlat organlari va ularning vakolatlari (Government agencies and their powers that carry out environmental control)" by B. Kalonov, "O'zbekiston respublikasida ekologik qonunchilikni tizimlashtirish va kodifikatsiyalash masalalari (Issues of systematization and codification of environmental legislation in the Republic of Uzbekistan)" by D. Safarov and J. Kholmominov's articles entitled "Ekologik xavfsizlikni ta'minlash va ekologik tahdidlarni oldini olishning huquqiy asosi (Legal basis for ensuring environmental safety and prevention of environmental threats)" within the framework of his research on the current issues of the history of Uzbekistan, focusing on the political, economic, cultural life of the country and the issues of international cooperation in these areas. - those who analyzed the historical foundations of environmental problems, their causes. At the same time, some information on the issues of international environmental cooperation can be found in the published scientific and popular works.

At the same time, from publications published in our republic in the fields of economy, the articles entitled "O'zbekistonda ekologik turizmni rivojlantirishni boshqarish mexanizmini takomillashtirish (Improving the mechanism of management of ecological tourism in Uzbekistan)", F. Valieva's "Globalnye problemy ekologii" and N. Samigova's "Ekologicheskie posledstviya urbanizatsii i industrializatsii i sovremennosti", A. Umarov's "Mintaqa iqtisodiy salohiyatidan foydalanish samaradorligini oshirishning ekologik jihatlari (Environmental aspects of increasing the efficiency of the region's economic potential)" and G. Rakhimova's scientific research work "XX asr 50-90 yillarda Farg'ona vodiysi sanoat rivojining ekologik holatga tasiri (In the 50 century the Fergana Valley, the Fergana Valley affect the environmental situation of industrial development)" environmental policy of Uzbekistan, fulfillment of obligations in international agreements, information on Uzbekistan's foreign policy in economic studies also reflected.

In the historiographical analysis of the subject, it is important to highlight the researches of the historians of the country dedicated to various issues of the new and most recent history of Uzbekistan. In these scientific studies, they analyzed the historical foundations of the socio-ecological problems that have arisen in our republic, their causes and solutions.

D. Bobojonova's "O'zbekistonda millatlararo munosabatlar rivojining ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy omillari (Socio-economic factors of the development of interethnic relations in Uzbekistan)" [1], H. Yunusova's "Sotsialno-ekonomicheskie protsessy i dukhovnaya jizn Uzbekistana v 80-x godax XX veka" [2] and B. Isakov's "O'zbekistonda 80-yillarning ikkinchi yarmi-2000-yillardagi tarixiy o'zgarishlarning demografik jarayonarga tasiri (The second half of the 80s in Uzbekistan, Influence of historical changes in the mid-2000s on demographic processes)" [3], demographic processes of Uzbekistan, i.e. issues of changes in the spheres of birth, natural population growth and migration,

issues of external labor migration in connection with the increase in the number of labor resources, internationalization of the perfect generation in Uzbekistan reflects the issue of education in the spirit of harmony and tolerance. After all, the main directions of international cooperation on nature protection are determined by the principles of the foreign policy strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan (nation-state interests of the country, norms of international law, non-interference in the internal affairs of other countries, peaceful resolution of all controversial issues).

In the scientific research work of O. Komilov entitled "O'zbekistonda irrigatsiya tizimini rivojlantirish va uning oqibatlari (Development of the irrigation system in Uzbekistan and its consequences) (1951-1990)" [4], during the years of Soviet rule, the construction of many hydrotechnical structures in Uzbekistan, the fact that they mainly served to improve the republic's cotton industry, and the policy of cotton monopoly is at the heart of it taking into account the growing shortage of water resources, rational use of water from transboundary rivers in Central Asia, improving the efficiency of the technical condition of existing large hydro facilities, ensuring their safety and reducing their negative impact on the environment and the lives of the population, focused on drawing up and implementing agreements. At the same time, considering that water is the source of life, today we must develop and sign mutual agreements under the initiative of prestigious international organizations in order to establish a rational and effective use of its reserves and to introduce the drip irrigation method to the agricultural sector of all countries of the region, to prevent drinking water shortages. ideas such as establishing the Central Asian Interstate Water Management Commission and establishing its activities on ensuring and eliminating food security related to water supply and food security.

In the scientific research work of S. Davletov entitled "XX asr ikkinchi yarmi – XXI asr boshida O'zbekistondagi ekologik vaziyat va uning ijtimoiy muammolari (Environmental situation in Uzbekistan and its social problems in the second half of the 20th century - the beginning of the 21st century)" [5], the feasibility of forming an environmental history society in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the issue of further research into the issues of interaction between nature and society, in order to improve ecological knowledge and skills, he emphasized the introduction of special educational courses "Barqaror taraqqiyot va tabiatdan foydalanish asoslari (Fundamentals of sustainable development and use of nature)" into the curricula of history, ecology, economy, and agriculture in higher education institutions. In addition, considering the importance of the widespread introduction of technologies using renewable energy in achieving the goals of sustainable development, increasing the targeted projects that promote the technical capabilities and socio-economic effectiveness of the effective use of alternative energy sources and resource-efficient technologies, is related to the dynamic growth of the population in the country and the further increase of the well-being of the population. considering the growing demand for food, he justified the need for effective use of innovative and resource-efficient technologies in agriculture, and the need to further strengthen the integration of science and production.

M.Rakhimov's nomination "Sotrudnichestvo Respubliki Uzbekistan so spetsializirovannymi uchrejdeniyami OON 1991-1999 gg (na primere UNESCO)" and "Sotrudnichestvo Uzbekistana c zarubejnymi stranami i mejdunarodnymi organizatsiyami v obespechenii stabilizati i ustoychivogo razvitiya v Tsentralnoy Asia (1991-2010 gody)" [10], D.M.Rahimbaeva's "O'zbekistonda diplomatiya xizmatining shakllanish va rivojlanish tarixi (1944–2001 yillar. Tashqi ishlar vazirligi misolida) (History of formation and development of the diplomatic service in Uzbekistan (1944-2001. As an example of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs))" and D.Saifullaev's "Mustaqillik davrida O'zbekiston diplomatiyasining shakllanishi va rivojlanishi (Formation and development of

Uzbekistan's diplomacy in the period of independence)" [6] in the research works, the issues of international environmental cooperation were specially addressed, taking into account the changing international relations and international politics, in this regard, the development of integration processes between the countries of Central Asia, the ways of jointly solving the social, economic, especially environmental problems that have arisen were discussed. Also, in this group, it is possible to highlight researches dedicated to cooperation relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan with international organizations.

M. Rakhimov "Mejdunarodnoe sotrudnichestvo Uzbekistana v kontekte obespecheniya stabilitiya i ustoichivnogo ravzitiya v Tsentralnoy Azii" and "Sovremennaya istoriya vzaimootnosheniy Uzbekistana i stran Tsentralnoy Azii s vedushchimi gosudarstvami mira", A. Kyrgyzboev "O'zbekiston Respublikasining Osiyo mamlakatlari bilan xalqaro hamkorligi (International cooperation of the Republic of Uzbekistan with Asian countries)" and R. Farmonov, Q. Juraev's books entitled "Xalqaro munosabatlar tarixi (History of International Relations)" reflect the international relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the history of its emergence and development[7].

In the historiography of the history of ecological cooperation, books and pamphlets and scientific articles that highlight some aspects of cooperation with international organizations, including the socio-economic situation in the Aral Bay region, are of particular importance. The book "Ocherki zarubezhnoy istoriografii noveyshey istorii Respubliki Karakalpakstan" published by B.A. Koshchanov, T.A. Ametov, Ya.B. Genjemuratov, S.B. Koshchanova, S.R. Davletov's "Ecological situation in Uzbekistan and its social problems (the second half of the 20th century - the beginning of the 21st century)" [8], R. Ballieva's "Ethnokulturnye aspekty ekologicheskikh problem Priaralya", S.R. Davletov's "The role of the "GEF" Agency in improving the ecological situation in the Lower Amudarya region" [9]], "Quyil Amudaryo xududagi ekologik vaziatni sog'lomlashtirishda «GEF» Agentligining tutgan o'rni (The role of international projects in solving socio-ecological problems in the Aral Bay region)" [10], O.B. Abdimo'minov's articles entitled "O'zbekiston va BMT: Orol muammosi yuzasidan hamkorlik (Uzbekistan and the UN: Cooperation on the Island Problem)"[11] also describe environmental problems in Aral and the Aral Bay region and their elimination. cooperation relations with international organizations, achievements in this regard and issues to be resolved in the future are highlighted. Foreign publications covering some aspects of cooperation between the International Foundation for Island Rescue and the Regional Ecological Center of Central Asia can also be included in the second group.

R. Alimov's monograph " Markaziy Osiyo: umumiy manfaatlar (Central Asia: common interests)" is devoted to the important aspects of the security problem in Central Asia, the geopolitical factor of some world powers in the region, while Sh. Arifkhanov's book deals with the geopolitical situation, prospects for solving the main problems of regional integration, and creating a more stable environment for ensuring security in Central Asia. attempts are analyzed. U. Hasanov, F. Tolipov, R. Farmanov, K. Juraev, I. Bobokulov, I. Mavlyanov and M. Bakhadirov's studies analyzed the main directions and nature of geopolitical changes in Central Asia, formulated national security strategies for Uzbekistan and the countries of the region, classified existing problems, and provided threats.

Central Asian-related studies were carried out by historians from the CIS countries, primarily by Russian researchers - A. Akimov, V. Belokrinitskiy, I. Zvyagelskaya, A. Bogaturov, A. Kurtov, A. Perepelkina, E. Kozozhkina, D. Trofimova, S. Panarina, E. Safronova, O. Tikhonova, A. Kazantseva, S. Bepalova, A. Vlasov, M. Starchak, S. In their works, Yuna and others analyzed the

geopolitical situation, the political position of the states, the socio-economic development and foreign political relations of the Central Asian states. However, most of these studies are one-sided and focus on political aspects [12].

In the monograph of a group of authors on the topic "Tizimli transformatsiya va insonning barqaror rivojlanishi: O'zbekiston misolida (Systematic transformation and sustainable human development: the case of Uzbekistan)", the specific characteristics of systematic transformation and sustainable development of humanity in Uzbekistan during the past 25 years of independence were studied. In it, the initial conditions in the newly independent states of Central Asia and the economic, social and ecological processes that appeared during the subsequent transition period are studied from a comparative perspective [13]. Special attention is paid to the "Uzbek model". The positive impact of economic reforms on sustainable development, the main trends in the development of demography and labor resources, targeted work on education, health, environment, housing and social protection of the population are studied.

Summary. In fact, one of the urgent issues for Central Asian countries, especially the Republic of Uzbekistan, is to strengthen a healthy ecological environment, transition to a "green economy", combat climate change, desertification, biodiversity loss and other environmental problems. In this regard, the study of environmental aspects of the country's domestic and foreign policy is of urgent importance.

The analysis of the level of study of the topic shows that the history of the establishment and development of the international ecological relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan has not been studied separately in the context of historicity in Uzbekistan and abroad. Based on this, it is appropriate to further strengthen the study of the aspects of international cooperation of the Republic of Uzbekistan related to ecology and environmental protection, and in this process, it is appropriate to introduce the results of research conducted in various directions, including foreign research.

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